

The Impact of Small Games Proposed Program on Development of Emotional Intelligence in Summer Camps Children (9-11) Years Old

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>ORIGINAL RESEARCH PAPER RECEIVED : 14/01/2022 ACCEPTED : 23/02/2022 PUBLISHED : 01/06/2022</p> <p>KEYWORDS : EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE, SMALL GAMES, SUMMER CAMPS.</p>	<p>THE OBJECT OF THE STUDY AIMS TO IDENTIFY THE IMPACT OF A PROPOSED PROGRAM BASED ON SMALL GAMES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE IN SUMMER CAMPS CHILDREN (9-11) YEARS OLD, FOR THIS PURPOSE, WE USED THE METHOD OF AN EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH WITH AN EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN WHICH CONTAINS TWO GROUPS OF INDIVIDUALS, ON A SAMPLE COMPOSED OF 30 CHILD FROM KARMA CAMP BOUMERDESS. CHOSEN AS AN EXPERIMENTAL GROUP (15 CHILD) AND A CONTROL GROUP (15 CHILD), AND FOR DATA COLLECTION, WE USED A TOOL OF ACTIVATOR OBSERVATION FORM OF DANIAL GOLEMAN'S EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE SCALE AFTER COLLECTING THE RESULTS AND HAVING TREATED THEM STATISTICALLY, WE CONCLUDE THAT THE PROPOSED PROGRAM BASED ON SMALL GAMES HAS AN IMPACT IN DEVELOPING EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE CAMP'S CHILDREN. ON THIS BASIS, THE STUDY RECOMMENDED TO INTRODUCE THE PROPOSED SMALL GAMES PROGRAM IN CAMPS AND TRAINING, TAKING ACCOUNT THE DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN'S EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE.</p>
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1. Introduction

We all have experience of childhood; not only as children but also in bringing up children, working with children or simply being members of society that values childhood, Children are a common part of our physical and social Landscape. (Wayness, 2019).

A child is born as a white page, and doesn't know anything about himself, but he makes some moves and emotions through which he expresses his organic needs, such as eating, dressing, sleeping and drinking, etc., growing in an environment where he learns the principles of life stage by stage, that share a single characteristic which is the basis for crossing these stages naturally, and which has been built by a group of scientists, namely, play.

Play is so important to optimal child development that it has been recognized by the United Nations High Commission for Human Rights as a right of every child. (Kenneth.R. Ginsburg, 2007).

However, the play allows children to use their creativity while developing their imagination, dexterity, and physical, cognitive, healthy brain development and emotional strength. (Shonkoff JP, 2000).

Therefore, play affects directly a child's mental abilities and its components, such as cognition, attention, understanding and intelligence. Besides, it is divided into several types: physical, musical, athletic, social, and emotional intelligence.

A wide range of research findings from the field of psychology, most notably from the scientist Goleman which defined the emotional intelligence as the ability to identify, control one's emotions, use feeling to generate self-motivation, empathized with others and build a good relationship with others.

Emotional intelligence is relatively new and growing area of behavioral investigation, having matured recently with the aid of previous studies related to this concept. A large number of studies with adolescents further suggest that the capacity of to decode, understand, and regulate emotions, interaction with other people, manage relationship associated with social and academic adjustment. (Malek, 2011).

Goleman also confirmed that problems facing an individual at present do not require uniquely mental abilities to solve them, but it need also emotional and social skills that belong with a child's emotional intelligence. That will help the child to achieve tangible benefits in terms of teaching

motor skills, motor balance, effectiveness, and physical and mental growth. (Al-Roumi, 1999).

These games are simple in their laws and regulation can be performed even in small spaces, and in small members and large tools without them, and was in our study in the group of games aimed at developing some elements of fitness under study by activity. (Kadri, 2017).

Many Scientifics call on attention to and nurturing childhood is one of the most important features of modern education and one of the indicators by which the progress and development of society is measured, Many psychologists and sociologists have gone to study childhood because of its great impact on the formation of the child's personality and the development of cognitive abilities. (Moufida, 2020).

And between the studies that use small games and emotional intelligence, we find a study of Nabil Mohamed Nadjh have confirmed the effectiveness of small games training to increase motivation (cognitive-achievement-activation)to learn passing skills, the study aimed to suggest a learning style with small games to increase motivation of 13-14 years players. (Nadhj, 2019).

The purpose of this study of Mahmoud Ben Saidwas to know the extent to games like sports affect social interaction in the sample of autistic children at the educational center for mental disabled El bayadh.(Said, 2020),The study of Noor-Azniza,Ishak also with to examining the effect of emotional intelligence training in raising the level of social and academic adjustment. (Noor-Azniza, 2011).

Furthermore, Khodja Asma's study aimed to reveal the relationship between emotional intelligence and happiness in second year secondary students. (Asma, 2018). All these studies confirmed that small games develop the desire for children to play and learn, and contribute to achieve their happiness and well-being.

This can be reflected positively in the level of their emotional intelligence, which is associated with a child's emotions, which can be revealed in different settings: School, family, environment, organized trips, and summer camps.

Summer camps are aimed to developing the social spirit of the children involved, expanding their intellectual and mental consciousness, and instilling a lot of moral and social values, in addition to spreading the spirit of social cooperation among children, the camps work to refine the child's personality, besides providing an atmosphere of fun and happiness and drawing smiles for a short time, through them, the child is used to use and

invest leisure time, which takes him away by swerving and hanging around, the camps also aim to promote a climate of democracy, equality and collective participation in activities and to restore this approach to their working lives.(Alwan, 2018).

The objective of the study is to realize a program based on small games to developing emotional intelligence, using the Activator observation form of Danial Goleman's Emotional Intelligence Scale, as well as to see if there were any differences between the two groups, experimental and control in the results, we used the experimental method as it is compatible with the nature of the research problem, and we also chose the design of method of the equivalent groups (experimental and control) with the pre- and post-measurement).

The question of this study is: How does a small games proposed program impact on development of emotional intelligence in summer camp children (9-11 years)?

Hypotheses:

- The proposed program based on small games has an impact on development of emotional intelligence in the camp's children.
- There are statistically significant differences between the averages scores of the members of the experimental group on the Activator observation form of emotional intelligence scale in the two measures, pre-measure and post-measure, and in favor of the post-measure.
- There were no statistically significant differences between the averages scores of the members of the control group on the Activator observation form of emotional intelligence scale in the pre and post measure.
- There are statistically significant differences between the averages scores of the experimental group on the Activator observation form of emotional intelligence scale and the mean scores of the control group after applying the proposed program in favor of the experimental group.

1.1. Literature Review

Emotional Intelligence: Emotional intelligence (EI) has been a subject of great interest to researchers in different areas. Higher EI is related to mental, psychosomatic, and physical health outcomes, In the educational context, higher EI is related to better academic performance and negatively related to aggressiveness, for teachers, it is negatively related to burnout. (Marchena-Giraldez, 2021).

Emotional Intelligence (EI): which is sometimes called emotional competence, has been defined as encompassing an individual's ability to

perceive, interpret, and regulate other's and one's own emotions. (Armstrong, 2015).

Small Games: The small games are simple organized games in which more than one person is involved to compete according to the given rules, they are not limited to agenda, age or physical level and they are predominated by recreation and entrainment, they can be with tools or without them.(Isam, 2019).

Childhood: Childhood is defined as the period of minority, which lasts from birth until adulthood(majority). The age of maturity varies by place and purpose. For example, in the United States, at age 18, you are considered an adult for military service, but a minor for buying alcohol. (Grewl, 2021).

Summer Camps: Summer camp is a place in the country where parents can pay to send their children during the school summer holidays, the children staying there can take part in many outdoor and social activities. (Dictionary, 2021)

2. Method and Materials

2.1. Participants

We use in our study a sample of 30 child among 170 children from karma camp, Boumerdes province.

2.2. Materials

Activator observation form of Danial Goleman's Emotional Intelligence Scale

The activator observation form include 25 sentences distributed according to the five dimensions established by Goleman for the expression of emotional intelligence, with each dimension we find five sentences corresponding to three answers. The activator has to choose the appropriate answer, thus bringing the total maximum score of the scale to 50 scores.

Proposed Small games Program

The date of application of the program was between 16-8-2019 and 30-8-2019.

The program includes 28 educational class, spread over 15 days. Each class has three principal stages: the preparatory phase, the main stage and the final stage. Each class differs from the other in the main stage, that contine three different small games.

So, we can use 84 small games that have been distributed equally to the classes programmed.

Validity and Reliability

Validity:

Construct Validity: the veracity of the construction was calculated by calculating the correlation coefficients between each dimension. The following table represents the total score of scale:

Table 1. The correlation coefficient between each dimension and the total score of the scale

Dimensions	The correlation coefficient between each dimension and the total score of the scale	
Self-awareness	,566**	
Self- regulation	,469*	
Empathy	,411*	
Motivation	,490*	
Relationship Management	,713**	
	Significant at the level 0,05	*
	Significant at the level 0,01	**

Source: made by ourselves from Spss

Intrinsic Validity: intrinsic Validity was calculated by the square root of the coefficient reliability, with a result of 26.27, a high intrinsic Validity.

Reliability:

Coefficient reliability with split-half method: this route was based on splitting the questionnaire into two parts, comprising the first part of paragraphs 1 to 13 and the second part of paragraphs 14 to 25, and then calculating the correlation coefficient.

Table.2 The results of reliability with split-half method

Scale	Value	Part 1	Coefficient reliability
,419			
13a	Number of elements		
,406	value	Part 2	
12b	Number of elements		
25	Component total		
,722			Correlation coefficient spearman-brown
,723	Correlation coefficient T Guttman Split-Half coefficient		

Source : made by ourselves from Spss

Coefficient reliability with Alpha-Cronbach: The alpha-Cronbach equation has been used to calculate the coefficients of the internal consistency of the scale and its sub-dimensions, and the following table shows the results:

Table3. Coefficient's reliability for each dimension and the total score of scale

Dimensions	Alpha Cronbach coefficient between each dimension and the total score of scale
Self-awareness	,658
Self-regulation	,681
Empathy	,690
Motivation	,684
Relationship Management	,610
Total scores	,690

Source : made by Ourselves from Spss

2.3. Design and Procedure

After agreement of the administration of Camp KARMA Boumerdess and after getting information about the sample and study's possible

problems, we made a plan to resolve them using the experimental design of two groups (control and experimental).

Table4. The Experimental design of the study

Groups	The pre-measurement	Experimental processing (independent variable)	The post-measurement
Experimental	Activator Observation Form of Daniel Golman's Emotional Intelligence scale	Proposed program (28 educational units)	Activator Observation Form of Daniel Golman's Emotional Intelligence scale
Control	Activator Observation Form of Daniel Golman's Emotional Intelligence scale	No program is applied to this group	Activator Observation Form of Daniel Golman's Emotional Intelligence scale

Source : made by Ourselves from Spss

2.4. Statistical Analysis

Statistical processing was done by SPSS version 25, which was used to calculate validity and reliability and to analyze the results of the field study based on:

Arithmetic mean. Sample T test Independent. Samples T test paired. The Alpha Cronbach coefficient, Pearson's correlation coefficient. Shapiro-wilk Test, spearman, Eta Squared Test η^2 , Cohen's coefficient (d).

Results

Table 5. Differences in the pre- and post-measurement for total score of experimental group and for each dimension of emotional intelligence scale

Dimensions	Groups	N	Arithmetic mean	Standard Deviants	df	Value T	Statistical significance (sig)
Emotional Intelligence scale	Self-awareness	Pre	6,8000	1,14642	14	-1,784	.096
		Post	7,4667	1,68466			
	Self-regulation	Pre	7,1333	2,03072	14	-2,578	.022
		Post	8,0000	1,25375			
	Empathy	Pre	3,4667	1,35576	14	-6,942	.000
		Post	8,2667	2,25093			
	Motivation	Pre	6,2000	1,56753	14	-3,761	.002
		Post	7,1333	1,06010			
	Relationship Management	Pre	7,4000	1,24212	14	-2,316	.036
		Post	8,6000	1,50238			
Total score	Pre	31,0000	4,73588	14	-5,424	.000	
	Post	39,4667	4,20657				

Source: made by ourselves from SPSS

The above table indicates that the calculated value of T is - 5,424 in the total score of Activator observation form of emotional intelligence scale is significant in the degrees of 14 freedom, which means that there are statistically significant differences between the two measurements in the level of emotional intelligence, where the arithmetic mean of pre-measurement is valued at 31,0000 with a standard deviation of 4,73588, which is less than the arithmetic mean of the post-measurement estimated at 39,4667 with a standard deviation of 4,20657. This means differences between the two measurements in favor of post-measurement.

Table 6. Effect size of applying a small games-based program on the development of emotional intelligence in the sample using the Cohen coefficient

Dimensions	Pre-measurement	Post-measurement	D	Effect Size	
Emotional Intelligence scale	Self-awareness	6,8000	7,4667	0,463	High
	Self-regulation	7,1333	8,0000	0,541	High
	Empathy	3,4667	8,2667	2,580	High
	Motivation	6,2000	7,1333	0,697	High
	Relationship Management	7,4000	8,6000	0,871	High
	Total score	31,0000	39,4667	1,890	High

Source: made by ourselves from SPSS

This table indicates that the value of “d” is 1,890 which is high. That means that there is an effect size of the proposed program on the

development of emotional intelligence on the experimental sample compared to the controlled sample.

Table 7. Differences in the pre- and post-tests for control group in the level of emotional intelligence.

Dimensions	Groups	N	Arithmetic mean	Standard Deviants	df	Value T	Statistical significance (sig)
Emotional Intelligence scale	Self-awareness	Pre	6,0000	2,26779	14	3,601	<u>.003</u>
		Post	3,8000	3,40588			
	Self-regulation	Pre	5,6667	2,19306	14	,649	<u>.527</u>
		Post	5 ,0667	3,08143			
	Empathy	Pre	4,4667	2,44560	14	1,126	<u>.279</u>
		Post	3,8667	2,99682			
	Motivation	Pre	4,2667	1,83095	14	2,636	<u>.020</u>
		Post	2,3333	1,75933			
	Relationship Management	Pre	4,6000	,82808	14	1,317	<u>.209</u>
		Post	4,0000	1,64751			
Total score	Pre	15	25,0000	4,92805	14	2,910	<u>.011</u>
	Post		19,0667	8,63933			

Source: made by ourselves from Spss

From the table, the calculated value of T is 2,910 in the total score of Activator observation form of emotional intelligence scale is significant in the degrees of 14 freedom, which means that there are no statistically significant differences between the two measurements in the level of emotional intelligence, where the arithmetic mean of Pre-measurement is valued at 25,0000 with a standard deviation of 4,92805, which is bigger than the arithmetic means of the post-measurement estimated at 19,0667 with a standard deviation of 8,63933; thus, there is no differences between the two measurements.

Table 8. Comparison between the control group and the experimental group after application of the proposed program in the level of emotional intelligence.

	Dimensions	Groups	N	Arithmetic	Standard	df	Value T	Statistical significance (sig)
				mean	Deviants			
Emotional Intelligence scale	Self-awareness	Control	30	3,8000	3,40588	28	-3,737	,001
		Experimental		7,4667	1,68466			
	Self-regulation	Control	30	5,0667	3,08143	28	-3,415	,002
		Experimental		8,0000	,25357			
	Empathy	Control	30	3,8667	2,99682	28	-4,547	,000
		Experimental		8,2667	2,25093			
	Motivation	Control	30	2,3333	1,75933	28	-9,051	,000
		Experimental		7,1333	1,06010			
	Relationship Management	Control	30	4,0000	1,64751	28	-7,990	,0000
		Experimental		8,6000	1,50238			
Total score	Control	30	19,0667	8,63933	28	-8,222	,000	
	Experimental		39,4667	4,20657				

Source: made by ourselves from Spss

The above table indicates that the calculated value of T is 8,222 in the total score of Activator observation form of emotional intelligence scale is significant in the degrees of 38 freedom, which means that there are statistically significant differences between the two groups in the level of emotional intelligence, where the arithmetic mean of control group is valued at 19,0667 with a standard deviation of 8,63933, which is less than the arithmetic mean of the experimental group estimated at 39,4667 with a standard deviation of 4,20657, that means that there are differences between the two groups in favor of experimental group.

An ETA square has also been calculated to see the impact of the proposed program on the level of emotional intelligence.

Table 9. Effect size of applying a semi-athletics games-based program on the development of emotional intelligence in the sample using the ETA square η^2 coefficient.

	Dimensions	Control Group	Experimental Group	η^2 ETA Square	Effect Size
Emotional Intelligence Scale	Self-awareness	3,8000	7,4667	,333	High
	Self-regulation	5,0667	8,0000	,294	Low
	Empathy	3,8667	8,2667	,425	High
	Motivation	2,3333	7,1333	,745	High
	Relationship Management	4,0000	,86000	,695	Average
	Total score	19,0667	39,4667	,707	High

Source: made by ourselves from Spss

The table indicates that the value of “ETA square η^2 ” is 0,707 which is high, this indicates the effect size of the proposed program on the development of emotional intelligence on the experimental sample compared to the controlled sample.

3. Discussion

1-From the table (6) we notice that there are statistically significant differences between the averages scores of the members of the experimental group on the emotional intelligence scale in the two measurements, pre-measurement and post-measurement, in favor of the post- measurement. The results of total score of the emotional intelligence scale were equal to -5,424, which is a significant value.

This explains the effectiveness of the proposed small games program, and from the answers of activators on the emotional intelligence scale, we note its positive impact. The results of the current study were consistent with the Karmich Ahlem& Belkasm Tawass study, to highlight the role of small games in the development of the social interaction during the physical and sports education of middle-class students.

Social skills are one of the dimensions of emotional intelligence that the proposed program has greatly influenced, that’s because we used small games which fit the study sample. (Tawass, 2019).

Attoui Amer’s study, aims to know the role of small games in the emotional development of the social aspect of high school students, it’s also agrees that small games, which are included in educational courses, play a major role in the development of social emotion, and developing spirit of responsibility and cooperation, through the emergence of the motivational

factor to the learning and the acquisition of the tendency to practice training classes using small games.

Furthermore, the emergence of a spirit of community, sportsmanship, respect for the law and others, social integration, self-confidence, an emotion control. (Amer, 2017).

All of these elements are in the form of the five dimensions of emotional intelligence: Self-awareness, self-regulation, empathy, motivation, relationship management, where the proposed program confirmed its positive and significant impact on the emotional intelligence scale through the activator observation form.

This is, of course, due to the importance of small games, which can change one's life in all aspects, physical, cognitive, etc. It's so special that it suits all ages, being a tool of development and improvement using of a legalized and viable program.

This has been demonstrated by the proposed program in its effectiveness in developing emotional intelligence in the sample of the experimental group.

Table (6), which calculates the high value of Cohen(d), estimated at 1,890 in the emotional intelligence, shows the impact of the proposed program, in a review of previous studies, we found in the results of Nesilhan Arikan's study the effect of sport education model-based on social-emotional learning program on emotional intelligence. (Arikan, 2020).

This supports the current study in calculating the scale of the program's impact on the development of emotional intelligence as a recent study. It also suggests the exact tools and statistical methods to obtain results that demonstrate the credibility of the program and the level of emotional intelligence of children.

2-It can be observed from table (7) that there are no statistically significant differences between the averages scores of the members of the control group on the emotional intelligence scale in the pre and post measurements. Although, the arithmetic averages for both the pre and post measurements were low in the level of emotional intelligence in the control sample members.

The results of the total scores of pre-measurements of the emotional intelligence scale were 2,910, and the arithmetic average was 25,000 And the post-measurements is valued at its arithmetic average 19;0667.

One reason for these results may be a lack of activities and small games. Moreover, the researcher has sought to the control sample members to ensure that they did not participate in the proposed program.

Also, the lack of good knowledge by trainers of the athletic aspect and their pros in creating a child-friendly atmosphere, which affects the control sample members. The pressure on training from strict rule-making obligations is also negative for children, which translates the non-significant T value in the emotional intelligence scale 2,910.

3-Through the results of the table (8), we have determined that there are statistically significant differences between the averages scores of the experimental group on the emotional intelligence scale and the mean scores of control group after applying the proposed program in favor of the experimental group. This is due to the proposed program.

which means that this program based on the small games has an impact very effective, as it has led to a significant development of emotional intelligence in the experimental group compared to the control group that was not exposed to the program.

The results of table (9) show that the ETA square value is 0,707, which is high. These results may be traced back to the small games used in the proposed program, which were consulted by experts and specialists, making the program legalized and applicable in accordance with the conditions set for it.

They were easy, simple, interesting and competitive, which contributed to the creation of homogeneity between the members of experiment sample, their self-awareness, their empathy and discovering their social skills, both with each other and with others, where these small games have raised their motivation.

These findings are consistent with the Ayta Mohamed Ali El-zabidi's study, which confirmed the effectiveness of using a counseling program for developing emotional intelligence in primary school pupils.

This program has contributed to touching all dimensions of emotional intelligence and highlighting their importance. (El-zabidi, 2019).

A study by El-djradat Ayat Ibrahim Ayada also recommended the importance of emotional intelligence in one's life not only in childhood but also for being an influential factor and offers opportunities for success, through the use of a program based on social and emotional games in development of emotional intelligence of kindergarten children. (Ayada, 2018).

It can be said that this is what its findings from our study have been confirmed by the proposed program of small games in the development of emotional intelligence.

A study by Ibtisam Radh also confirmed the differences in level of emotional intelligence, which found that there is a difference between males and females in the proportion of emotional intelligence. (Ibtisam, 2014).

We have sought to apply the proposed program taking into account all the conditions for achieving the goal of the program, which has proved that it is effective (effect size) through the results obtained.

4. Conclusion

Emotional intelligence has become a vital part of how people face the great challenges that matter to their lives, and that is what we have tried to prove in this study.

Moreover, we were able to answer the problem of our research that is the impact of the proposed program based on small games in developing emotional intelligence in the summer camp's children using the activator observation form of Danial Goleman's Emotional Intelligence Scale

finally, we suggest to: adopt and introduce the proposed small games program in camps and training and use a new and diverse program, taking account the development of children's emotional intelligence.

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